

Errors Analysis on the use of Adjective Clauses: The Application of Dulay's Surface Strategy Taxonomy at University Students

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Abstract

This study is concerned with the errors made by the students of the English Education Study Program at Tadulako University in forming adjective clauses. The purposes of this study were to categorize the kinds of errors and to identify the most common errors made by the students while using adjective clauses. Data for this study were gathered through the analysis of written texts using a descriptive qualitative methodology. The focus of this research was the errors in using relative pronouns who, whom, which, and whose that were examined using Dulay's Surface Strategy Taxonomy. The participants of this research were 45 students chosen purposively. The results showed that the most common error made by the students was misordering, followed by addition, misformation, and omission respectively. The role of the teachers to cope with the committed errors is discussed.

Introduction

Grammar courses are compulsory in the English Education Study Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Tadulako University, Palu, Indonesia. The grammar courses are divided into four levels, Basic Communicative Grammar Skills, Elementary Communicative Grammar Skills, Intermediate Communicative Grammar Skills, and Advanced Communicative Grammar Skills. They are successively scheduled in four semesters, semesters one, two, three, and four. Adjective Clause is part of the topics that are programmed in Advanced Communicative Grammar Skills and is taught in two face-to-face sessions. Student mastery in adjective clauses varies at the end of each semester and is often programmed remedial course for those who did not pass Advanced Communicative Grammar Skills Course.

Grammar is vital for students to improve their language skills and language component mastery. A sound command of grammar can help students create proper sentences that lead to effective writing (Jubran, 2021; Rambe et al., 2021). Therefore, students should be proficient with longer construction, and clauses, to be able to compose compound and complex sentences. The various clauses can be used to enhance the student's ability to communicate and to improve the quality of their writing. There are three kinds of clauses included in the instructional materials for Advanced Communicative Grammar Skills, noun clause, adjective clause, and adverb clause. The present study specifies the investigation and analysis of the adjective clauses. The students can use adjective clauses to provide more details, avoid unnecessary repetition, and make compound sentences easier to understand.

Literature Review

An adjective clause that occurs after the noun and pronoun are explained is a dependent clause that gives information about nouns. It is preceded by the relative adverbs, namely *when*, *where*, and *why* or relative pronouns *who*, *whom*, *which*, *whose*, and *that*. Each relative pronoun that can be used as a possessive word, subject, or object serves a specific purpose (Azar, 2002). Research results indicate that there are many students find it challenging to learn adjective clauses (Al Baroroh & Hani, 2020; Astuti, 2013; Haryani & Fatimah, 2020; Koçak, 2020; Kusumadewi, 2019; Ramadhan et al., 2019). Al Baroroh and Hani (2020) revealed that students faced difficulty to identify particular subject or object when applying an adjective clause in sentences, Astuti (2013) revealed that students lack knowledge of arranging words to form adjective clauses and lack understanding of adjective clauses, Koçak (2020) noted that the students found it difficult to determine when an adjective is acted as an object of a verb, Kusumadewi (2019) reported that students got difficulties to form correct adjective clauses and to determine the function of relative pronouns, Haryani and Fatimah (2020) highlighted that students struggle to choose appropriate relative pronouns for various adjective clause forms, and Ramadhan et al., (2019) argued that it is still difficult for students to understand adjective clauses in a reading text. Consequently, quite a few students commonly run into issues and commit errors when they construct adjective clauses. The error committed by the learners must be analyzed by language experts or

teachers (Brown, 2007) by applying error analysis (James, 1998) so that strategies to improve the student's mastery of the use of adjective clauses can be developed.

Error analysis has long been practiced in language teaching to find out the gap between the target language and the native language of the learners. Error analysis is defined as the process of identifying the prevalence, characteristics, root causes, and effects of failed language (Deveneyns & Tummers, 2012; James, 1998) and the errors in language learning have been classified into four types; linguistic category, comparative taxonomy, communicative effect taxonomy, and surface strategy (Dulay *et al.*, 1982, in (Bochari *et al.*, 2019). Bochari *et al.*, (2019) further argued that the linguistic category organizes errors based on linguistic elements, namely those linguistic constituents that contribute to the error's effects, phonological errors (pronunciation), morphological and syntactic faults (grammar), semantic and lexical errors (meaning and vocabulary), and discourse are all examples of language components (style). Comparative taxonomy categorizes errors by contrasting the structure of constructions that are errors in second language acquisition with other types of constructions. Additionally, communicative effect taxonomy examines errors in terms of their impact on the reader or listener. This taxonomy focuses on separating errors that appear to lead to misunderstandings (global error) from those that do not (local error). The surface strategy, meanwhile, emphasizes how surface features are changed. Finding the cognitive mechanisms underlying the learner's reconstruction of the new language is its main focus. The surface approach taxonomy includes the error types of omission, where students omit certain linguistic forms because of their complexity in production, addition, where students add redundant items in addition to omitting elements they believe to be unnecessary, selection, where students make mistakes in pronunciation, morphology, syntax, and vocabulary by choosing the incorrect phoneme, morpheme, structure, or vocabulary item, and order, where students commit an error in morphological level misordering (Bochari *et al.*, 2019; Brown, 2007; Kafipour & Khojasteh, 2012).

Researchers revealed that due to the students' attempt to apply the rules of their mother tongue to the foreign language's grammar, which differs from their native language grammar, students frequently make mistakes when learning the grammar of a foreign language or the target language (Brown, 2007; Budiharto, 2019; Hamed, 2018; Kafipour & Khojasteh, 2012). Brown (2007) emphasizes that an error is a clear departure from the grammar of a native speaker, demonstrating the learner's proficiency. It implies that an error is a deliberate departure made by speakers of the target language who have not yet mastered its rules. Because an error reflects a learner's current developmental stage or underlying competency, learners are unable to self-correct. It indicates that the presence of foreign language teachers cannot be neglected (Brown, 2007; Gass & Selinker, 2001; Manurung, 2015). The teacher is needed to analyze factors that have caused learners to commit errors. The analysis of these factors needs the comprehensive role of EFL teachers so that the results of the analysis can facilitate the teaching of grammar of English in general and clauses in particular.

Research problem

Error analysis is a systematic method to identify and analyze the errors made by learners to obtain information on common difficulties in learning languages. The result of error analysis could inform the teachers about the errors and difficulties faced by the students in their language learning (Richards, (2002) in Nzerem & Bob, 2021)). The teachers can develop their teaching materials and prepare for the challenging topics that their students have encountered. The roles of foreign language teachers are needed to analyze and revise students' errors. The roles of foreign language teachers are to understand and thoroughly analyze the errors so that solutions to the errors can be offered both to the learners and the language teachers. Based on the advantages of analyzing errors committed by EFL learners, this study investigates answers to the following research problems; 1) what errors are committed by EFL learners in constructing adjective clauses at the English Department, Faculty of Teaching Training and Education, Tadulako University Palu?, and 2) What errors are the most frequently committed by the EFL learners at the English Department, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education in constructing adjective clauses?

Method

Design of the Study

This research applied a descriptive qualitative design. The descriptive design is used to collect data by following a systematic process of collecting, categorizing, estimating, and analyzing the data (Creswell, 2014). 45 students were chosen as the research participants. This research used a purposive sampling technique and took all students who have passed the Advanced Communicative Grammar Skills course in the 2021/2022 academic year.

Data collection and analysis

The worksheet of the students on adjective clause formation in the Advance Communicative Grammar Skills class where the researchers were teaching was collected. The errors committed by the students were analyzed. The technique of the analysis was based on the procedure of error analysis, data were collected, and identified by sorting the right and wrong answers, and then the identified errors were evaluated and classified

into four types based on Dulay *et al.*,(1982); omission, addition, misformation, and misordering. Finally, the frequency of each type of error was calculated to find out the most frequently committed errors by the students.

Results and Discussion

Types of Errors Committed by The Students of the English Department

The students at the English Department, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education Tadulako University Palu commit four types of errors in constructing adjective clauses. The four types of errors are in line with Dulay's Surface Strategy Taxonomy (Dulay *et al.*, 1982). The types of errors committed are omission, addition, misformation, and misordering. The frequency of the errors committed is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The Frequency of Students' Errors Based on Surface Strategy Taxonomy

The result of the data analysis as seen in Figure 1 confirms that there are 59 errors in omission, 76 errors in addition, 76 errors in misformation, and 107 errors in misordering. Misordering errors are therefore the most common form of errors produced by students. Below are descriptions of the errors committed by the students in constructing adjective clauses in each category.

Errors of Omission

The results of the data analysis revealed the students commit errors in the omission of relative pronouns, nominative pronouns, subject complement, inflectional suffixes, indefinite articles, primary auxiliary verbs, and copula (linking verb). Relative pronouns are important since these are the ones that introduce an adjective clause. Without relative pronouns, adjective clauses would not exist. However, more than 20 of 45 students did not include it in their sentences. This confirms the findings of Gustira *et al.*, (2020) that the students often omitted relative pronouns when using adjective clauses. The nominative pronoun is a pronoun that can act as the subject of the sentence. Every complete sentence contains two parts: a subject and a predicate. Nevertheless, some students omitted the subject. As the result, their sentences become ungrammatical. For instance, students commonly provided answers like *She is someone who used to know her*. This sentence is incorrect because the students did not only use inaccurate relative pronouns but they did not also put the nominative pronoun *I* as the subject that performs the verb *used to know*. The subject complement is a word that comes after the linking verbs and renames, identifies, or describes the subjects. Nevertheless, as shown in the students' answers, some students left out the subject complement in their sentences. They wrote *I used to know who she is*. The sentence contains a linking verb or copula *is*. Therefore, it requires a subject complement to complete the sentence. The sentence must be *She is someone whom I used to know*. An inflectional suffix is a word part that is added to the end of a base word that changes the number or tense (Richards (1992) in Siyaswati (2019) states that inflection is:

The process of adding an AFFIX to a word or changing it to some other way according to the rules of the grammar of a language. For example, in English, verbs are inflected for 3rd- person singular: I work, he/she works, and for past tense: I worked. Most nouns may be inflected for plural: horse-horses, flower-flowers, man-men.

The results of the data analysis reveal that there are students who made errors by omitting the suffix *-s* which serves as a plural marker. They wrote *the key* instead of *the keys*. In addition, they omitted the suffix *-s* as 3rd person singular marker. They wrote *a guy who dance really well*. In this sentence, the subject is *a guy*. Therefore, the verb must be *dances*. These errors are due to the structural difference between English and Indonesian. Unlike English grammar, Indonesian does not require word form by adding *-s/-es* to introduce plural nouns and 3rd person singular subjects. In the omission of the indefinite article, errors are committed both in definite and indefinite articles. An article is a word used to modify a noun, which is a person, place, object, or idea. It can be divided into an indefinite article and a definite article. An indefinite article *a/an* is always connected to a singular noun (Azar, 2002). Among the students' answers, one student omitted the indefinite article *a* before the singular noun. He wrote *She invited guy to the party who dances really well* instead of *She*

invited a guy who dances really well to the party. In the same case in the omission of auxiliary verbs, errors are also committed by the students both in primary auxiliary verbs and modal auxiliary. An auxiliary verb helps the main verb to describe an action, show the tenses, and to form a negative statement or question. It is also called a helping verb. There are two kinds of auxiliary verbs; primary auxiliary verbs such as: *is, am, are, was, and were* and modal auxiliary verbs: *can, might, will, etc.* Wardhaugh (2002) as cited in Luvuno & Ajani (2021) states that: “*any misuse or omission of auxiliary verbs in focus, distorts messages’ meant to be sent.*” (p. 70). Nevertheless, the students commonly omitted the primary auxiliary verb *be* in their sentences. They wrote *The key which I looking for all day were in my shoe.* The correct answer should be *The keys which I was looking for all day were in my shoe.* The last error in omission is linking verbs or copula. A copula is a term that refers to a linking verb *be*. Eastwood (2002) as cited in Sulaiman *et al.*, (2022) defines the copulative verb as a linking verb that needs a complement (an adjective phrase or a noun phrase) relates to and describe the subject. According to the result of data analysis, using copulative verbs or linking verbs in sentences seems to be a confusing issue for some students. The most common problem in using the copula *be* is that the students tend to omit it. They made some errors by writing *The keys which I was looking for them all day in my shoe* which must be written *The keys which I was looking for all day were in my shoe.*

Errors of Addition

The addition is a type of error that is characterized by the presence of an item that must not appear in a well-formed utterance. Errors committed in addition are related to possessive adjectives, nominative pronouns, objective pronouns, auxiliary verbs, transitive verbs, definite articles, adverbs, and prepositions. Possessive adjectives are used to show possession or ownership of something. MacFayden (2015) in Syahdan & Putri (2020) explains that when a pronoun is possessive, it functions as a marker of ownership and identifies the owner of a specific thing or person. Possessive adjectives consist of: *my, your, her, his, our, their, and its.* In the adjective clause, the possessive adjectives must be replaced by the relative pronoun *Whose*. Nevertheless, 22 students added possessive adjectives in their answers. Their sentences mostly looked like this: *The people whose we visited their house were very welcoming.* The sentence must be written as follows: *The people whose house we visited were very welcoming.* Errors in addition of nominative are related to the use of *which* and *who*. When combining two separate sentences into a single sentence with an adjective clause, the students must change the pronoun to the relative. Therefore, the relative pronoun always replaces the pronoun at the beginning of the adjective clause. The students tend to add unnecessary nominative pronouns in forming sentences. They commonly add those pronouns right after the relative pronoun *which* and *who* as a connector. The students also committed addition errors by adding objective pronouns. One student wrote *She is someone that I used to know her.* The objective pronoun *her* is not necessary for this sentence since it must be replaced with a relative pronoun. Likewise, 14 students added the pronoun “them” as an objective pronoun in *The keys which I was looking for them all day in my shoe.* Errors are also committed in addition to primary auxiliary verbs. Primary auxiliary verbs *be, do, have* often appeared alongside other verbs for various grammatical reasons. They may be necessary to form questions or different tenses. However, they are not always required. The students made addition errors by adding unnecessary primary auxiliary verbs *be* such as *is* and *was*. The addition of transitive verbs is also committed by the students. In one of the research data, it is found out an addition error of transitive verb. The student’s answer is *The girl is someone whom I want to know.* This sentence is incorrect since it contains the transitive verb *want* that does not exist in the question. The addition of article is also an error that is committed by the students. Some students put an additional definite article in their sentences. The sentence looks like this: *The people were the house we visited was very welcome.* The students wrote *the house we visited* to refer to the subject at the beginning of the sentence. However, since the instruction is to combine the sentences using a relative pronoun, the definite article *the* in *the house* should be omitted. The right answer is: *The people whose house we visited were very welcome.* The addition of the adverb of time is another error by the students. It is noted that one student committed an error in the addition of an adverb. She wrote *The people were very welcoming, who ever visited their house.* The student should write *The people whose house we visited were very welcoming.* The students added an adverb of time *ever* after the relative pronoun *who*. The last error committed in addition is the unnecessary use of prepositions. Indonesian student wrote *I was looking for the keys were in my shoe for them all day.* This sentence is not effective because the students added more information by using the preposition *for* twice in their sentences. The student should have written as follows: *The keys which I was looking for all day were in my shoe.*

Errors of Misformation

Errors of misformation are related to the unnecessary use of the relative pronoun, verb, participle adjective, and subject-verb agreement. The students tend to make misformation errors when forming sentences with adjective clauses. They failed to understand the use of different relative pronouns. As a result, they often put incorrect relative pronouns in their sentences. For instance, misformation errors occurred in which the students were expected to use the relative pronoun *whom* as the object of a verb. It must be written *She is someone whom I used to know.* However, the students were not able to distinguish the subject and the object in a sentence. As a result, most of them used the relative pronoun *who* as a subject rather than *whom*. The findings also indicate that

the students frequently made errors by using the wrong verb form. For example, *The people whose house we visited were very welcoming* was written by the students as follows: *We visited their house who the people are very welcoming*. They put an auxiliary verb *are* instead of *were* as a past tense marker. A past tense marker is required because the sentence contains the past verb *visited* in *We visited their house*. The students also commit errors by using unnecessary participle adjectives. For example, The students wrote: *The people were the house we visited was very welcome*. The sentence is incorrect because the student used the participle adjective *welcome* after a primary auxiliary verb *was*. When using auxiliary verbs *be*, the students must use the *verb+ing* form of participle adjective. Therefore, the correct answer must be: *The people whose house we visited were very welcoming*. The students also committed errors in subject-verb agreement. According to Nordquist (2018) in Mesrawati & Narius (2019), subject-verb agreement is the correspondence of a verb with its subject in person (first, second, or third) and number (singular or plural). It is also called subject-verb concord. It means that the subject should agree with the verb. However, the students failed to understand that a primary auxiliary verb *is* used as a singular verb while *were* function as a plural verb. Thus, in the context where they are expected to use plural primary auxiliary verb *were*, they use singular auxiliary verbs *is* and *was* instead, not minding whether the tense is correct or not. The students wrote: *The people were the house we visited was very welcome* and *The people where we visited their house is very welcoming*. These are clear signals that they are not always conscious of the principles guiding the use of the English primary auxiliary verbs (*be*) whenever they communicate in English. This is a result of the differences between Indonesian and English language structures. The verbs in an Indonesian sentence remain the same whether the subject is singular or plural and whether the action takes place in the present, in the past, or in the future. English verbs, on the other hand, are always dependent on the subject and the time of an action (tense).

Errors of Misordering

In English, the position of the adjective clause always follows the noun and pronoun being explained. However, in the student's answers, the adjective clause was placed quite far away from the nouns it modifies. It indicates that the students do not understand the rules for putting the adjective clause in a sentence. Misordering is also the case in the research from Saputra *et al.*, (2020), where misordering has the highest frequency (80.95%) based on the student's answers. Students made errors because they used the Indonesian speaking style to build sentences. As a result, their word order often resembles Indonesian patterns.

The findings imply that Indonesian students have committed errors in constructing adjective clauses. The most frequently committed error is misordering. It implies that *misordering* is complex for Indonesian students and therefore the teaching of the adjective clause must be revised. It has been argued that the teaching of language must be started from the simple items to the more complex ones (Manurung, 2017; Richards, 2001), and consequently, the teaching of adjective clauses in the Indonesian context shall be done in the following order; *omission*, *misformation*, *addition*, and ended up by *misordering*. These difficulties can be understood because *misordering* does not exist too often in Indonesian and misordering in an Indonesian sentence does not totally change the meaning of a sentence. However, this difficulty must be overcome because more and more Indonesian students are interested to pursue their degree in a native country of English where formal or academic writing is required. It means that the role of the teacher is needed to improve effective writing strategy and to achieve quality academic skills (Rambe *et al.*, 2021) and supported by contextual instructional materials (Manurung, 2015). Contextual instructional materials in teaching adjective clauses are needed so that the students can use them in their daily encounters. By using the clauses in the students' daily activities the clauses can be kept in their long-term memory.

Conclusion

Complex sentences containing an adjective clause are often used incorrectly by the students. The most common type of error committed by the students is *misordering* followed by *omission*, *misformation*, and *addition* respectively. The students make misordering errors by putting the adjective clause in the wrong position in a sentence because they failed to understand that the adjective clause should come after the noun it modifies. The role of the teachers is required to decrease errors occurrences in the students' sentences by analyzing the errors. The results of the error analysis are used to classify and grade the error so that effective instructional materials organization can be done before the teaching and learning process. By having the results of the error analysis the teacher can also choose the right teaching strategies to present the prepared and designed instructional strategies. The teachers have to take into account the importance of the position of the noun in forming the adjective clauses correctly. This can be conducted by the teachers by providing the students with a more precise explanation by demonstrating the sentence constructions contextually.

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